

The Interrogation of the Mob Killing of Deborah Samuel in Sokoto on the Ground of Blasphemy and Its Implication for Peaceful Coexistence

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Abstract

There is no religion in Nigeria that does not believe in the existence of the Supreme God, and that He rewards and rebukes those who do good and bad respectively, since everyone is aware of these consequences, we all try to do good to everyone that comes our way. Unfortunately, overtime, fanaticism crept into the practice of religion. Among the attendant consequences is spirit of intolerance both within and between adherents of the two major religions in Nigeria, Islam and Christianity. The exercise of brutality to exhibit intolerance and fanaticism worsen rivalry within and between adherents of both religions. The brutal killing of Deborah Samuel, a student of Shehu Shagari College of Education Sokoto is one of such recent incidents which has aggravated the rivalry between the adherents of Islam and Christianity in Nigeria. The paper examines the mob killing of Deborah Samuel in Sokoto on the ground of blasphemy and its implication for peaceful coexistence. The paper uses descriptive survey method for data collection and analysis. Effort have been made to proffer recommendations for taming the incidents of religious intolerance and fanaticism.

Keywords: Examination, mob killing, blasphemy, implication, coexistence

Introduction

All the religions believe in the existence of a Supreme God who rewards everyone for doing good and punishes those who do evil. Consequently, everyone tries to do good to be rewarded by the Supreme God who is in control of the Universe. Even the founders of Christianity and Islam, which are the two major religions in Nigeria, clearly demonstrated love of fellow human beings no matter the race and religious affiliations. Similarly, the two religions share common teachings. For instance, both Muslims and Christians affirm that there is only one God who is fundamentally simple, mysterious, and incomprehensible. They believe, God created the world, and sought to relate with his human creatures, and desired a human response of undivided worship and service.

Like the Christians, the Muslims believe in Monotheism (Tawhid): they also believe in monotheism which is the cornerstone of the Islamic religion. They believed that there is no other God but Allah (Shahadda). Similarly, they believe that all the Prophets sent by God to humanity shared the same central themes, and that was the message of monotheism, which is a term used to refer to the belief in the existence of only one God whom they believe created the universe, the heavens, the earth, the stars, the mountains, the oceans, humans, animals, plants and everything else in existence. Ironically, they also believe that one can fight on behalf of God (Surah 2:244) just as we can see from the case of the killing of Deborah Samuel in Sokoto as the story explains so many things.

Circumstances of the mob killing of Deborah Samuel in Sokoto, Nigeria

Miss Deborah Samuel was a 200-level student of Shehu Shagari College of Education, Sokoto, who was murdered in cool blood and her corpse burnt by her fellow students on allegation of blaspheming the Prophet (pbh) on 15 May 2022. Lafiagi, a Muslim brother, states in support of the murder of Deborah that; “I bear witness that none has the right to be worshipped but Allah and that prophet Muhammad is the messenger of Allah, affirm the absolute dignity and honor of our leader, Muhammad, and condemn in totality any disrespect or insult to the personality of the prophet.”¹ The Muslims in Nigeria seems to adhere to the above statement more than anything else in the Qur’an especially the later part of the statement above that talks about disrespect to the person of the prophet.

A keen look at the audio clips that precipitated what was alleged to be the case of blasphemy against Deborah which eventually led to her brutal murder, we discovered some vital issues that I will love to share; as follows:

- i. Miss Deborah was a 200-level student of the College who had stayed in the college for more than a year with her fellow school mates sharing issues on the same WhatsApp group that created the problem that led to her death.
- ii. Deborah did not just wake up to insult the prophet.
- iii. She merely reacted to an incident when her school mates turned the WhatsApp group to be a platform for expressing their religious messages outside the purpose to which the group was created.
- iv. The main aim of the group was to create awareness on fixed classes, changes in class times and dates, announcements for assignments and other related academic matters other than religion.
- v. Deborah only questioned her mate who turned the group into a platform for strong Islamic religious activities other than the main aim of the group, especially when the group has adherents of different faiths in it.

To properly understand the Genesis of what resulted to the mob killing of Deborah, it is important to recap a testimony by one of her course mates. According to the testimony, her classmate asked her how she passed her last semester’s examination, and she responded that it was Jesus oh! When she was asked to retract the statement, she refused and shouted “Holy Ghost fire, nothing will happen to me” She acted based on the things her course mates have been sending on the WhatsApp group. She asked why others send similar messages and nothing happens and when she replied someone and was asked to retract her statement. Following her refusal, the Muslim students made invitation to some people who were not part of the school community to invade the school in search of Deborah in connection with her response. In the process, some of her class mates helped her to escape and took her to the college security post for safety. Unfortunately, the security personnel were over powered by the people who were invited to kill Deborah.

The questions at this juncture are: How true? Was it that the people who were invited threatened to kill anyone who stood on their way? But whatever was the answer, she was dragged out, flogged, stoned to death and her corpse set ablaze. One sees the killing of Deborah as the fulfilment of the scriptural verse in the book John 16:2b-3 which states that; “a time is coming when anyone who kills you will think he is offering a service to God, they will do such thing because they have not known the father nor me.” This is why to the Muslims who believe in what happened to Deborah, her killing was seen as rendering service to Allah, the God of the Muslims, which the scripture makes it clear that they do so because they do not know God.

Reactions by some Renowned Islamic clerics on Deborah’s Brutal Murder

It is interesting to note that many renowned Islamic scholars condemned Deborah’s killing. For instance, one of Nigerian’s popular Islamic scholar, Sheikh Gumi, in *Premium Times* of 15th May, 2022, reacted to the killing of Deborah in his Kaduna Mosque that; “anyone who killed a non-Muslim who they have agreed to live peacefully with, will not smell the fragrance of paradise for four years” (Hadith 49).² He said the Prophet himself was insulted several times at different points yet he did not attack or kill anybody who assassinated his character. The Sheik made this known in his Kaduna Mosque while conducting prayers. He said, the best a Muslim can do

to show he or she loves the Prophet is by adhering to his teachings. In the same vein, the Chief Imam of Masjid Al Nabawi in Medina, Saudi Arabia, Sheikh Ali Al Hudaify, condemns the mob killing of Deborah Samuel in Sokoto. He warns that such violent act will make people flee from accepting Islam.

It is no doubt that the comments by the aforementioned Islamic clerics are proofs that the clerics have proper knowledge of Islam in an ideal state that is different from the abnormal version being displayed in Nigeria which led to the killing of Deborah. Lack of proper Knowledge is a major factor that kills must of our religious adherents.³ When one does not have accurate knowledge on the teachings and beliefs of other religions, one should not be hasty in judgment. Unfortunately, both Christians and Muslims in Africa are good at making conclusions on things they do not know. There is a lot of ignorance and prejudice in the practice of religion in Africa.⁴ This is why maintaining peace among religions has become a major problem in Africa, for peace is something you make but not something you wish.⁵

The Nature of Christians' Reaction to Cases of Grave Blasphemy by Eminent Muslim Personalities

Similar issues of blaspheming happened in Nigeria against Christianity by adherents of Islamic religion, but the question is, how did Christians react to such cases in order for peace to prevail? For instance, Abubakar Suleiman, Sterling Bank Managing Director, was involved in a case of blasphemy but the Church did not kill him, there was not even a protest of any kind or any deadly reaction from Christians, except a mild caution or reaction by the Christians Association of Nigerian (CAN). We thank God for remorse exhibited by Abubakar, who apologized and was forgiven by the CAN for the purpose of harmonious co-existence. His blasphemy was that he compared our Lord and Savior Jesus Christ with Agege bread. There is no doubt that if it were to be a Christian who blasphemed against Mohammad that way, heaven would have been set loose.

A similar case of Abubakar was the case of Nasir Ahmad El-Rufai on 27th January, 2013, who twitted on his twitter handle that; ‘If Jesus criticizes Jonathan’s Government, Maku/Abati/Okupe will say he slept with Mary Madgalene.’⁶ Yet, for peaceful coexistence, no one said anything but the comment was taken as a joke, he mentioned names of personalities on the twit that was so strong of a joke. Imagine this was done using the name of Prophet Muhammad, heaven would have been let loose. But it is important to take note that no religion has the monopoly of arrogance and Terrorism. Most recent, at the occasion of the declaration of the Muslim-Muslim ticket which created a lot of tension in the country, the leadership of the All Progressives Congress (APC) alongside with it Presidential candidate and his running mate, Asiwaju Bola Ahmad Tinubu and Mallam Shettima, respectively, contracted some devious people to act as Bishops at the occasion yet the Christians did not react violently. However, there were mere demand by some Christians who asked Shetima and the APC to disclose the identity of persons who masqueraded as Bishops and their respective denominations.⁷ Similarly, on 3rd August, 2022, the National Chairman of the All Progressives Congress (APC), Senator Abdullahi Adamu went into an ECWA Church in Nasarawa State with his cap on his head, mounted the pulpit with his cap on his head shouted ‘praise the Lord, Halleluyah. The Lord is good!! This was an act of mockery to the Christian faith but nothing was done to him. Rather, he received a rousing applause from the congregation. But if similar thing was done in a mosque by a Christian, the person in question could not have gone out free.⁸

Prophet Muhammad’s (SAW) teachings on response to Blasphemy by his true followers

Imam Khurshid states that;

Islam tends to establish peace. If this peace is disturbed, then accordingly actions are to be taken to preserve peace in the society. The Quran perfectly makes balance between these two scenarios. Prophet Muhammad was labelled and ridiculed by his opponents as: “A madman” (Quran 15:7 2). “There is madness in him” (Quran 23:71 3). “A victim of deception” (Quran 17:48 4). “Poet” and “a fabricator” by the disbelievers (Quran 16:02).

There is no place yet, not for once, that the Qur’an or the Prophet himself commanded that such blasphemous person should be killed. There were a lot of people who attacked the personality of the Prophet, they attacked the

Qur'an, calling it a book of "confused dreams". If all of these would have happened in our present-day Nigerian society, the people would have been killed. Indeed, the Holy Qur'an itself points to the fact that they saw its instructions as "mere stories of the ancients" (Quran 16:25). The Quran says that the biggest abuse against God is for one to claim that God has begotten a Son. Even then, the Quran (Quran 19:88-92) did not say anyone should kill such a person.⁹ If there is anything we can say the Quran teaches us is utmost high morals. In similar vein, the Quran has not laid emphasis on punishment, anarchy or fear but rather on explanation, reconciliation and deterrence. So much care does the Quran take in dealing with other faiths that it teaches not to speak bad words even for the false gods (Quran 6:108). Similarly, Islam preaches establishing peace in both the life of the society and of an individual. This is why if something is resulting in disturbance of the peace of the land, in an ideal situation, Islam does not allow it.¹⁰ The big question, then, is, where do we have the Qur'anic teachings that permitted the brutal mob killing of Deborah by a group of Islamic adherents?

The Biblical Teachings on the Love for Neighbours

The Bible in its multiple teachings has commanded the Christians to live in love with their neighbours, few among the scriptures we shall be considering here. It is important to note that love for one's neighbor as for himself or herself is the second of the two great commandments Jesus gave to His followers. He commanded them to first love God with the whole of their heart, mind and soul, and followed by the love for their neighbours as the second great commandment. The second commandment is seen by all believers as a fundamental consideration in dealing with their neighbours, as God first showed by loving us (John 3:16). Jesus explains that if you can love your neighbor and love God you have fulfilled all the law and the Prophet. Both the law and the Prophet hang on the two.

It is important to note that Jesus was very explicit on the concept of a neighbor in His response to the Pharisees' probing question; "Who is my neighbor?" Instead of giving a direct answer, Jesus Christ turned the question on the Pharisee by telling the parable of the Good Samaritan. The parable tells the story of a man who was attacked by robbers on the road to Jericho. He was stripped of his clothes, beaten, and was left to die. Soon after, a priest was passing by the same road and when he saw the man, he went to the other side of the road and continued on his way. A Levite then passed by, and he too moved to the other side of the road when he saw the man. But a Samaritan came by and when he saw the man, he took pity on him, poured oil and wine on his wounds, carried him on his donkey and brought him to an inn and took care of him there. The following day, he gave the innkeeper two denarii and asked him to look after the man, adding that when he returns, he will compensate the innkeeper for any extra expense he may have. After telling the story, Jesus asked the Pharisee which he thought among the three, was a neighbor to the man who was robbed, to which the Pharisee replied, "The man who showed mercy." Jesus then told the Pharisee to go and do likewise (Luke 10:25-37).

Jesus taught us that it is not about asking who our neighbour is. Rather, it is about our own willingness to be a good neighbour ready to love. In a similar scripture, Christians are instructed that; No one should seek their own good, but the good of others (I Corinthians 10:24). Those who you are living with, your neighbours, are the first point of call for every Christian. If you want to fulfil the law then you must love your neighbor as much as you love yourself. For the entire law is fulfilled in keeping this one command: "Love your neighbor as yourself" (Galatians 5:14).

Similarly, the scripture enjoins us to keep on loving one another as brothers and sisters. The scripture admonishes us not to forget to show hospitality to strangers, for by so doing some people have shown hospitality to angels without knowing it (Hebrews 13:1-2). Even in showing hospitality, the scripture admonishes that we should "Do nothing out of selfish ambition or vain conceit. Rather, in humility, value others above yourselves (Philippians 2:3). Fundamentally, Love is the only virtue Christ urges his followers to keep doing, show hospitality to everyone that life may bring to you. This does not exclude those who either offend us or blaspheme against God.

What Nigerian Christians Need to Know and Do According to the Scriptures

It is no doubt that the books of the Old Testament originated from the teachings of Judaism which is based on the Mosaic laws of eye for an eye. However, as Christians, we are expected to follow the teachings of our Lord and Savior Jesus Christ. This is because, while the Old Testament teachings promote violence, the New Testament teachings preached by Jesus preaches peace. For instance, we have Old Testament teachings such as “whoever sheds the blood of man, by man shall his blood be shed; for in the image of God made man” (Genesis 9:6); “If a thief is caught breaking in and is struck so that he dies, the defender is not guilty of bloodshed” (Exodus 22:2); “If a man digs a pit, he will fall to it, if a man roll a stone, it will roll back on him” (Proverbs 26: 27); “If anyone is to go into captivity, into captivity he will go, if anyone is to be killed with the sword, with the sword he will be killed. This calls for patient endurance and faithfulness on the part of the saints” (Revelation 13:10).

However, Jesus’ teachings in the New Testament do not present the picture of violence for violence. Rather, we have teachings such as; But I say to you who hear, love your enemies do good to those who hate you; bless those who curse you; pray for those who mistreat you; whoever hits you on the cheek, offer him the other also; and whoever takes away your coat, do not withhold your shirt from him either (Luke 6:27-36). In similar vein, Jesus, teaching His disciples, said; In everything, therefore, treat people the same way you want them to treat you, for this is the law and the prophet (Matthew 7:12); the response of man should not be on the basis of how one is treated but on how one wants to be treated; Blessed are the peace makers, for they shall be called the sons of God (Matthew 5:9); Bless those who persecute you; bless and do not curse them (Romans 12:14-21). “Do not repay anyone evil for evil ...” (Rom 12:17a). “Do not take vengeance, but leave room for God’s wrath, for it is written; it is mine to revenge, I will repay, says the Lord” (Rom 12:20); “if your enemy is hungry, feed him; if he is thirsty, give him something to drink. In doing this, you heap coals on his head” (Rom 12:20); “Do not be overcome by evil but overcome evil with good” (Rom 12:21).

Our Lord Jesus practicalised His teaching on love, even for our enemies, when He was being crucified. His prayer for those crucifying him was “Father, forgive them, for they do not know what they do ... (Luke 23:34). Indeed, He had all the power needed to react and even create tension in the city but He looked at those crucifying Him and prayed good for them. Similarly, even for the people who mocked Him, asking Him to save Himself since He saved others still Jesus did not prove otherwise.¹¹ It is imperative at this juncture to commend the adherents of Christ for adhering to these teachings about their relationship with their neighbours and even for those who persecute them. Similarly, even Prophet Muhammad preached love for fellow Muslims, and even for non-Muslims. According to him, it is when Muslims show love to non-Muslims that they can easily woe them to follow their religion. But the big question remains, if Muhammad preached love for even non-Muslims, and even demonstrated it, which verse (s) do those who claim to be fighting for Allah always refer to?

Implications of the Mob killing on Christian Muslim Relation

Loss of lives and property

Most religious crises have been bloody with several lives lost, including the destruction of property worth millions or billions of naira. In similar vein, the reactions that followed the killing of Deborah led to so much destruction and looting of properties. Street boys who were waiting for such an incident took advantage to loot shops belonging mostly to Igbo and other Christians. The counter reactions that followed equally affected adherents of the other faith. Properties worth millions of naira were lost in the process. This was confirmed by Sule who testify on a similar incident in Wukari where such incident occurred.¹²

Politics of Religion

Religion has infiltrated the political system with Nigerian politicians resorting to exploiting religion to achieve their selfish gains. Churches and Mosque are seen as very good avenues for political campaigns and related activities. This usually accounted for why individuals are always voted not based on their capability but on religious affiliations (Sunday 67). This has become the order of the day in Nigeria where politicians always

take advantage of any incident to promote religious politics. The case of Deborah is seemingly producing the same ripples effects in the ongoing political dispensation. The incident has contributed in producing the type of seemingly hostile atmosphere being produced. It has become common place to hear both Christians and Muslims openly campaigning on religious lines in churches and mosques respectively. The dimension the trend is assuming, if God does not intervene, Nigeria is likely going to experience very bloody political scenario in the forthcoming 2023 general election.

Impact on the Economy

The ethno-religious crises in Nigeria have continue to have great impact on the economy. Most rises usually have damaging effect on the economy, especially on the immediate economic environment they occur. They usually have cumulative on the centre economy. For instance, the Maitastine crisis in Yola in the early eighties and the Boko Haram episode which began in the last part of the first decade of the 21st century. This development has continued to discourage foreign investors in investing in the country.¹³ The case of Deborah in Sokoto has created a similar scenario as many foreign investors in particular, see Sokoto as very dangerous place to invest. This is because the investments of some individuals were destroyed in addition to the disruption of economic activities and destruction of property. Even to date total normalcy been restored in some key places that were destroyed by the activities of few who took advantage of the incident to loot and destroy properties. This has adverse effect on economic activities in the area. It has equally thrown fear to potential, both local and foreign investors in the area.

Suspicion between the Two Faiths

Religious crises are very active variables that institutes fear, hatred, and suspicion among and between adherents of different faith almost the world over. In Nigeria, since the beginning of the introduction of religion in politics, particularly between the adherents of the two major religion, the crack between adherents of the two religions has continued to widen. Even brutal murder of Deborah by Islamic fanatics in Sokoto has added momentum to the already widening gap between Christians and Muslims in the country. In fact, the incident has contributed enormously in the way the way and manner the religion factor has become prominent in the process of the mobilization of members of Christian and Islamic faiths for the forthcoming election in 2023. Even the choice of a Muslim-Muslim ticket has much to do with the effects of Deborah's murder which has added much momentum to the nature of religious politics being experienced presently in Nigeria. There is great fear that if the trend is not checked, religion will obviously become the determining factor for the voting by the followers of Nigerian's two major religions, Islam and Christianity.

Conclusion

At the moment, Nigeria is going through series of challenging issues especially tension between the two faiths.¹⁴ These issues and the tension they have generated and are still generating, range from Boko Haram, Fulani herdsmen attacks on, mostly Christian's communities kidnapping, banditry among others.¹⁵ The foregoing challenges have confirmed to produce ripples effects on the Nigerian society. At present, the development is increasing in threatening peaceful coexistence in Nigeria. The brutal killing of Deborah has added momentum to the unfortunate development, especially very disturbing rivalry between Nigerians two major faiths, Islam and Christianity. This has injected very poisonous venom in the unfolding political atmosphere. If the unity and corporate existence of Nigeria is to be sustained, there must be quick concerted efforts to tame the unfortunate tide. What is urgently needed to savage the situation, which one presents as recommendations.

Recommendations

- i. The two major religions, Islam and Christianity, especially adherents of Islam must be seen observing their religious tenets, prominent among which is love for fellow human being irrespective of socio-cultural, economic and political affiliations.
- ii. Observation of the spirit of tolerance for one another, as opposed to what is the current trend.
- iii. A very deliberate war against religious fanaticism by adherents of the two major religions.
- iv. Depoliticization of politics of religion.
- v. Leaders of the two major religious bodies should preach the message of peace to their adherents. And they themselves should be seen actively relating with the leaders of the other religion to prove to their adherents that they are also supporters of peace. They should also identify with each other during periods of bereavements or celebrations, especially when they are invited to attend. Which will help check the reoccurring of similar incident of Deborah, let it be seen from the leaders that we are one.
- vi. Forums should be created where discussions on issues relate to the development of the entire country are discussed within injecting religious issues into deliberation. In other word, the religious factor should not be at the centre of such discussions. Instead, adherents of Nigeria's two major religions, Islam and Christianity, should imbibe the spirit of respect for one another, as well as demonstration of tolerance for each other religious tenets.
- vii. Those caught in the habit of causing trouble and intimidating people should be made to face the wrath of the law, and justice should be meted out to everyone no matter how highly placed. This will serve as deterrent to those who might be nursing the idea of either attacking innocent people or instigating violence in any part of the country.

Endnotes

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